

The winter stonefly genus *Eucapnopsis* Okamoto, 1922 (Plecoptera: Capniidae) in Korea

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Abstract. The Korean distribution of the winter stonefly genus *Eucapnopsis* Okamoto, 1922 is reviewed, on the basis of available published and recently collected materials. Three species are confirmed: *E. brevicauda* (Claassen, 1924), *E. jirisana* sp. n. and *E. koreensis* sp. n. Previous records of *E. quattuorsegmentata* Okamoto, 1922 refer to *E. brevicauda*, while previous records of *E. stigmatica* Okamoto, 1922 probably refer to *E. koreensis*. The species *Eucapnopsis koreensis* is widespread and common in South Korea, while the transpacific *E. brevicauda* is rare in the country, and *E. jirisana* appears to be confined to the Jiri Mts. No records are known from North Korea. South Korean records are depicted on a map.

Keywords. *Eucapnopsis brevicauda*, *Eucapnopsis jirisana* sp. n., *Eucapnopsis koreensis* sp. n., South Korea

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Eucapnopsis* Okamoto, 1922 is a species poor group of winter stoneflies, widely distributed in the East Palearctic and the western part of Nearctic (DeWalt *et al.* 2024). There are five species and one subspecies described, but certain problems with species delimitation have been identified due to the high variability of a few reliable species-specific characters (Shimizu & Negoro 2003, Judson & Nelson 2012).

The first record of the genus from the Korean Peninsula was given by Yoon & Aw (1986). They briefly described and figured unidentified nymphs collected in South Korea, under the temporary name *Eucapnopsis* KUa. Later, Kim *et al.* (1998) reported adults from South Korea, attributed to the type species, *E. stigmatica* Okamoto, 1922. More recently, Hwang & Murányi (2020) published the first records of *E. quattuorsegmentata* Okamoto, 1922 adults from South Korea. The genus was not yet found in North Korea and neighbouring northeast China, but a further spe-

cies, *E. brevicauda* (Claassen, 1924) is known from the Russian Far East (Teslenko & Zhiltzova 2009). Based on large series recently collected by Malaise traps, and the available published specimens, we aim to revise the adults of Korean *Eucapnopsis* in the present paper. An integrative revision of the whole genus will be published subsequently (Murányi *et al.* in prep.).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens were collected by Malaise traps, beating sheet or by hand, fixed in 80% ethanol, some of their terminalia were cleared in KOH. Holotypes are deposited in the collection of the Entomological Museum of Korea University, Seoul, Republic of Korea (EMKU). Paratypes and further materials are deposited in the EMKU, the Department of Zoology, Eszterházy Károly Catholic University, Eger, Hungary (EKCU), and the National Institute of Biological Resources, Incheon, Republic of Korea (NIBR).

Illustrations were made with the aid of a drawing tube applied on a Nikon SMZ10 microscope, and a Keyence LHX5000 digital microscope. All images were adjusted and assembled into figures with Adobe Photoshop CC 2019. Terminology mainly follows our previous works (Murányi *et al.* 2014, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Eucapnopsis brevicauda (Claassen, 1924)

(Figures 1–5, 16)

Eucapnopsis quattuorsegmentata Okamoto, 1922: Hwang & Murányi 2020: 48 (records from South Korea).

Eucapnopsis brevicauda (Claassen, 1924): Murányi *et al.* 2026: in preparation. (for complete synonymy).

Material examined. South Korea: Mt. So-baeksan, Geumseon, Geumgye-ri, Punggi-eup, Yeongju-si, Gyeongsangbuk-do, N36°57'25.1" E128°25'47.6", 13.v.2016, sweeping, leg. Jong Cheol Jung: 1♀ (NIBR); Satancheon Stream, Sannasa valley, Yongjeon-ri, Okcheon-myeon, Yangpyeong-gun, Gyeonggi-do, 19.iii.2019, sweeping, leg. Jeong Mi Hwang: 25♀ (EMKU); Mt. Odaesan, Mireukam Temple, Odaesan-ro, Jinbunmyeon, Pyeongchang-gun, Gangwon-do, N37°48'12.82" E128°34'03.02", 23.vi.–vii.28.2020, Malaise trap, leg. Daseul Ham, Jeong Mi Hwang, Ji Hyun Kang, Sung Hwan Park: 33♂ 9♀ (EMKU); Mt. Bangtaesan, Bangdong-ri, Girinmyeon, Inje-gun, Gangwon-do, N37°54'29.57" E128°24'25.14", 690 m, iv.7 ~ v.11.2019, Malaise trap, leg. Daseul Ham: 2♂7♀ (EMKU).

Diagnosis: Cercomeres nearly cylindrical and 5 in numbers, apical ones elongated; body small sized and delicate, macropterous. Male tergum IX not raised, posteromedial lobe lacking but medial portion armed with scales; ventral vesicle large and elliptical; main epiproct sclerite high and rounded in lateral view, elliptical in dorsal and rounded quadrangular in frontal view, medioapical hole and ventroapical lobe moderate. Female subgenital plate pale without any dark markings, setation scarce, posteromedial lobe is lacking; anterior sclerites indistinct, pale; lateral sclerites

triangular, not lobed and well separated, bald area indistinct.

Description: Small sized, delicate species, both sexes macropterous. Forewing length: males 4.0–4.4 mm, females 4.2–4.6 mm; body length: males 3.4–3.6 mm, females 3.6–4.0 mm. Setation moderately dense and long. Cubital cell quadrangular, stigma indistinct but present. General color grey, sclerotization relatively weak.

Male abdomen (Figs. 1–4, 16): Tergum IX not raised in lateral view; posterior margin only slightly indented medially, armed with scarce scales and a few setae, median lobe lacking. Ventral vesicle present, its width is more than half of its length; subgenital plate rounded, about twice longer than vesicle. Paraprocts brown, lateral edges rectangular, tip elongated triangular. The main epiproct sclerite is high and broadly rounded in lateral view, highest in the medial half; elliptical in dorsal, rounded quadrangular in frontal view; ventroapical lobe weakly developed, apex relatively short and curved; dorsomedial division nearly straight, medioapical hole hardly distinguishable. Cerci with 5 nearly cylindrical segments, basal cercomeres short but apical one about three times longer than wide.

Female abdomen (Fig. 5): Subgenital plate entirely pale without dark markings; posterior margin nearly straight to rounded triangular, without medial lobe; setation limited to a few short setae on the lateral portions. Anterior sclerites pale, hardly distinguishable. Lateral sclerites medium sized, triangular and well separated, not lobed, medial tip is blunt and rounded, medial area between the lobes bears short but dense setae. Bald area of the sclerites large but indistinct, elliptical. Vaginal cavity with relatively wide opening. Cerci similar to that of male.

Affinities: Both sexes are very similar to the Japanese *E. quattuorsegmentata*, but they have more than four segments on their cerci. In addition, males of *E. quattuorsegmentata* usually have even higher main epiproct sclerite, and the lateral sclerites of the female terminalia usually with slight anterior lobes.

Figures 1–5. *Eucapnopsis brevicauda* (Claassen, 1924), Odaesan Mts. 1 = male terminalia, lateral view; 2 = same, dorsal view; 3 = same, ventral view; 4 = male cercus, dorsal view; 5 = female terminalia, ventral view. Scale 0.5 mm.

Distribution and ecology: The species has the widest distribution among its congeners: it is known from Canada, Mongolia, Russia and the USA. In Korea, the species emerge from sub-montane streams during March to May, and seems to be much more rare than *E. koreensis* (Fig. 16).

Remarks: In our previous paper (Hwang & Murányi 2020), we published the female spe-

cimens from Mt. Sobaek and the Satancheon Stream as the first records of *E. quattuorsegmentata* from Korea. By collecting a large number of specimens of both sexes from Mt. Odaesan, we revised our identification and concluded that *E. quattuorsegmentata* is restricted to Japan, while the Korean populations belong to the more widespread *E. brevicauda*.

***Eucapnopsis jirisana* sp. nov.**

(Figures 6–10, 16–17)

Type material: Holotype male: **South Korea:** Mt. Jirisan, Jungsanri Campground, Jungsan-ri, Sicheon-myeon, Sancheong-gun, Gyeongsangnam-do, N35°18'37.83" E127°45'05.47", 20.i–1.iv.2022, 721m, Malaise trap, leg. Yeon Jae Bae (EMKU). Paratypes: same locality and data 1♂ (EMKU), 1♂ (NIBR, NIBRIN0001025751); Mt. Jirisan, Bangmudong Campground, Gangcheong-ri, Macheon-myeon, Hamyang-gun, Gyeongsangnam-do, N35°21'03.11" E127°40'42.24", 20.i–20.iv.2022, 657m, Malaise trap, leg. Yeon Jae Bae: 1♂ 1♀ (EMKU), 1♂ 1♀ (EKCU).

Diagnosis: Cercomeres cylindrical and short, 3–4 in numbers; body medium sized and robust, slightly brachypterous. Male tergum IX not raised, ventral vesicle large and elliptical; main epiproct sclerite long, elliptical and apically dilated in lateral view, elliptical in dorsal and rounded in frontal view, lacks medioapical hole, ventroapical lobe moderate. Female subgenital plate pale with dark posteromedial patch forming a bar on posterior edge, scarce setae, posteromedial lobe indistinguishable; lateral sclerites quadrangular, not lobed and well separated, bald area indistinct.

Description: Medium sized, robust species, both sexes slightly brachypterous. Forewing length: holotype male 4.6 mm, paratype males 3.2–4.1 mm, paratype females 5.0 mm; body length: holotype male 5.2 mm, paratype males 4.8–5.1 mm, paratype females 5.6 mm. Setation generally dense and long. Cubital cell quadrangular, stigma indistinct but present. General color dark brown, sclerotization strong.

Male abdomen (Figs. 6–9, 16): Tergum IX not raised in lateral view, posterior margin deeply indented medially and armed with strong setae, median lobe and scales lacking. Ventral vesicle present, its width is less than half of its length; subgenital plate rounded triangular, more than twice longer than vesicle. Paraprocts brown, lateral edges rectangular, tip triangular. The main epiproct sclerite is long and elliptical in lateral view, only slightly higher medially than the

dilated portion before apex; elliptical in dorsal, rounded in frontal view; ventroapical lobe moderately developed, apex relatively long and moderately curved; dorsomedial division straight and surrounded by wide membranous portion, medioapical hole not distinguishable. Cerci with 3–4 cylindrical segments, cercomeres short, apical one about twice longer than wide.

Female abdomen (Fig. 10): Subgenital plate pale with dark posteromedial patch forming a bar on the posterior edge, not wider than one fifth of the plate's width; posterior margin rounded triangular with indistinguishable medial lobe; setation limited to a very few short setae on the lateral portions. Anterior sclerites hardly distinguishable. Lateral sclerites medium sized, quadrangular and well separated, not lobed and medial tip is quadrangular, medial area between the lobes bears very short but dense setae arranged in a posterior bar. Bald area of the sclerites large but indistinct, quadrangular. Vaginal cavity with relatively wide opening. Cerci similar to that of male.

Affinities: The male can be distinguished from its congeners by the dorsally elliptical, frontally rounded, and laterally elongated, elliptical, apically dilated main epiproct sclerite that lacks medioapical hole and bears moderate ventroapical lobe. The female genitalia is distinctive by pale subgenital plate ornamented by a posteromedial patch that is forming a dark bar on the posterior edge. Both sexes are relatively robust and dark colored, general appearance of both sexes are similar to *E. koreensis* and *E. stigmatica* but slightly brachypterous.

Distribution and ecology: The species was found at streams in the Jiri Mts. (Figs. 16–17), the highest part of the Sobaek ranges of the southern Korean Peninsula. The type locality is a mid-elevation forest stream with cold water. The specimens were caught by Malaise trap operated from late January to late April.

Etymology: The name *jirisana* refers to the Jiri Mts (Jirisan), where the new species was found and supposedly endemic to the mountains or its wider range. Used as an adjective, gender feminine.

Figures 6–10. *Eucapnopsis jirisana* sp. nov., Jiri Mts. 6 = male terminalia, lateral view; 7 = same, dorsal view; 8 = same, ventral view; 9 = male cercus, dorsal view; 10 = female terminalia, ventral view. Scale 0.5 mm.

***Eucapnopsis koreensis* sp. nov.**

(Figures 11–16, 18)

?*Eucapnopsis stigmatica* Okamoto, 192: Kim *et al.* 1998: 422 (records from South Korea).

?*Eucapnopsis* KUa Yoon & Aw 1986: 14 (description of the larva from South Korea).

Type material: Holotype male: **South Korea:** Yangyang Namdaecheon stream, Eoseongjeon-ri, Hyeonbuk-myeon, Yangyang-gun, Gangwon-do, 31.iii–20.iv.2023, 340m, N37°54'00.17" E128°39'04.68", Malaise trap, leg. Yeon Jae Bae (EMKU). Paratypes: same locality and data: 1♂ (EMKU),

2♂ 3♀ (EKCUCU); Mt. Odaesan, Odaesan-ro, Jinbunmyeon, Pyeongchang-gun, Gangwon-do, 11.v.–26.v.2019, 929m, N37°47'34.58" E128°33'37.97", Malaise trap, leg. Daseul Ham, Jeong Mi Hwang, Ji Hyun Kang, Sung Hwan Park: 1♂ (NIBR); lower section of the forest brook towards Sangwonsa Temple, Chiaksan National Park, Seongnam-ri, Sillim-myeon, Wonju-si, Gangwon-do, 850m, N37°18'02.8" E128°03'32.1", 14.v.2016, leg. Jeong Mi Hwang, Dávid Murányi: 1♀ (EKCUCU).

Diagnosis: Cercomeres moderately elongated, 5–6 in numbers; body medium sized and robust,

Figures 11–15. *Eucapnopsis koreensis* sp. nov., Odaesan Mts. 11 = male terminalia, lateral view; 12 = same, dorsal view; 13 = same, ventral view; 14 = male cercus, dorsal view; 15 = female terminalia, ventral view. Scale 0.5 mm.

macropterous. Male tergum IX not raised, ventral vesicle large and elliptical; main epiproct sclerite long, triangular in lateral view, elliptical in dorsal and rounded in frontal view, lacks ventroapical lobe, medioapical hole moderate. Female subgenital plate pale with small posteromedial patch positioned far from posterior edge, scarce setae, posteromedial lobe hardly distinguishable; lateral sclerites triangular, not lobed and well separated, bald area indistinct.

Description: Medium to large sized, robust species, both sexes macropterous. Forewing

length: holotype male 4.9 mm, paratype males 5.2–5.4 mm, paratype females 6.0–6.6 mm; body length: holotype male 4.5 mm, paratype males 5.0–5.2 mm, paratype females 5.4–6.5 mm. Setation generally dense but moderately long. Cubital cell quadrangular, stigma indistinct but present. General color dark brown, sclerotization relatively strong.

Male abdomen (Figs. 11–14, 16): Tergum IX not raised in lateral view, posterior margin weakly indented medially but armed with strong setae, median lobe lacking, few scales present. Ventral vesicle present, its length is one and half of its

width; subgenital plate widely rounded, more than twice longer than vesicle. Paraprocts brown, lateral edges rounded, tip blunt. The main epiproct sclerite is long and triangular in lateral view, highest medially; elliptical in dorsal, rounded in frontal view; ventroapical lobe lacking, apex relatively long and weakly curved; dorsomedial division sinuous, medioapical hole moderately developed. Cerci with 5–6 cylindrical to slightly clubbed segments, basal cercomeres short but apical 3 elongated to three times longer than wide.

Female abdomen (Fig. 15): Subgenital plate pale with dark small posteromedial patch positioned far from the posterior edge, not wider than one fifteenth of the plate's width, but sometimes only a hardly noticeable spot or furrow-like mark; posterior margin rounded triangular with hardly distinguishable medial lobe; setation limited to a few short setae on the lateral portions. Anterior sclerites hardly distinguishable. Lateral sclerites medium sized, triangular and well separated, not lobed and medial tip is sharply triangular to blunt or widely rounded, medial area between the lobes bears short but dense setae. Bald area of the sclerites large but indistinct, rounded elliptical. Vaginal cavity with relatively narrow opening. Cerci similar to that of male.

Affinities: The male can be distinguished from the other members of the *stigmatica* group by the dorsally elliptical, frontally rounded, and laterally triangular main epiproct sclerite that lacks ventroapical lobe but bears moderate medioapical hole. The female genitalia is distinctive by pale subgenital plate ornamented with a small posteromedial patch that is positioned far from the posterior edge. As detailed above, general appearance of both sexes is similar to *E. stigmatica* and the slightly brachypterous *E. jirisana*.

Distribution and ecology: The species was found at several localities in South Korea (Figs. 16, 18), at different elevations. The type locality (Yangyang Namdaecheon stream) originates from Odaesan National Park. The specimens were collected from March to May, mostly by Malaise traps but also by beating sheet and hand.

Etymology: The name *koreensis* refers to the wide distribution of the species in South Korea. Used as an adjective, common-gender.

Remarks: According to its size, the larva described as *Eucapnopsis* KUa from South Korea by Yoon & Aw (1986) probably refers to *E. koreensis*. Since the adults reminds to *E. stigmatica*, reports by Kim *et al.* (1998) from South Korea surely refer to this species.

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Figure 16–18. Distribution and habitat of Korean *Eucapnopsis* Okamoto, 1922. 16 = distribution on the Korean Peninsula, with lateral profiles of male main epiproct sclerites (grey areas are above 1000 meters); 17 = type locality of *E. jirisana* **sp. nov.** 18 = type locality of *E. koreensis* **sp. nov.**

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